

TEACHING UNIVERSITY STUDENTS IN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN MODERN CONDITIONS: TRADITION AND INNOVATION

Mahametova Dilnavoz Botirovna

Department of foreign languages,
Tashkent University of Information Technologies
Muhammad al- Khorazmiy (PhD)
dmahametova1979@gmail.com

ABSTRACT:

This thesis looks at how foreign language instruction is changing for University students in contemporary classrooms and examining the evolving landscape of teaching within modern educational settings. The study explores the relationship between innovative approaches and standard pedagogies and how it affects language learning and academic advancement. With an emphasis on communicative approaches, immersive experiences, technological integration, and the role of educators, this research attempts to give higher education institutions a thorough grasp of modern, efficient language teaching methods.

Keywords: *Immersive learning, educator role, modern pedagogies, innovation, traditional methods, technology integration, language acquisition, higher education, and communicative approaches.*

INTRODUCTION:

Teaching foreign languages to university students in today's educational environments requires a sophisticated approach that combines cutting-edge techniques with conventional pedagogies. This thesis provides an explanation of the changing nature of language instruction in higher education through a thorough investigation of technological integration, immersive experiences, communicative techniques, and the critical role of educators. The aforementioned research highlights the importance of achieving equilibrium between conventional bases and innovative methods in order to facilitate efficient language learning and comprehensive academic growth.

These days, there are many resources available thanks to technology breakthroughs that make language learning easier. Students can connect with the language outside of the classroom thanks to interactive software platforms, internet resources, virtual classrooms, and language learning apps that support traditional lectures.

Naturally, of course! Teaching foreign languages to university students in today's educational settings requires a dynamic fusion of traditional methods and innovative approaches. These elements come together to create a comprehensive framework for academic progress and language development.

Language acquisition in higher education has traditionally been controlled by textbooks, planned classroom sessions, and instruction that is grammar-focused. However, contemporary teaching methods have embraced innovation and included communicative approaches, immersive experiences, and technology to enhance language learning.

Thanks to technological advancements, there are a lot of materials available these days that facilitate language acquisition. Thanks to interactive software platforms, online materials, virtual classrooms, and language learning applications that supplement conventional lectures, students can stay in touch with the language outside of the classroom.

CONCLUSION:

The study shows that for comprehensive language learning, university students must be taught a foreign language using a combination of traditional and new methods. Technology is essential for improving educational experiences, and immersive learning offers unmatched chances to develop language and cultural awareness. Furthermore, teachers' flexible role as facilitators who blend conventional pedagogies with contemporary techniques has a big impact on students' language learning experiences. As a result, it is critical for language teachers to balance tradition with innovation in order to adequately prepare their pupils for life in a worldwide society and provide them with the language skills and cultural sensitivity needed to succeed in a variety of professional fields.

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